

The behavioral intention formation: the consumption of labeled product in Morocco

La formation de l'intention comportementale: la consommation des produits de terroir labellisés

RAIF Maha

PHD Student

The national school of trade and management of Agadir

Ibn Zohr - Morocco

MAPES

maha.raif@gmail.com

AIT HEDA Abdellatif

Professor

The national school of trade and management of Agadir

IBN ZOHR University in Morocco

MAPES

aaitheda@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT :

The interest in local products in Morocco is due to their participation in the economic and social development of Morocco. The Distinctive Signs of Origin and Quality (SDOQ) are a part of the strategies of valorization of those products. They protect both the cooperatives' products and their consumers.

This paper aims to investigate both the beliefs of Moroccans towards labeled locally grown products and the factors that might prevent their consumption. For this, our research is based on the Theory of Planned behavior of Ajzen (1991).

Given the limited number of studies on the consumption of the said products in Morocco, our objective is to get closer to the Moroccan consumer. We therefore opted for 17 focus groups composed by three persons per one.

Participants expressed a favorable attitude towards these products. However there are barriers that may prevent the act of purchase. Thus, lack of trust in state organisms was the most factor cited by respondents. It's followed by the proximity and exorbitant price of labeled products. From a managerial point of view, the knowledge of these trained beliefs about labeled local products will allow all stakeholders to adapt their offers according to consumers' expectations. This will, hopefully, encourage Moroccans to consume local products and participate in the social and economic development.

Additional Key words: local products; labeling; intention; beliefs; consumer behavior.

RESUME:

L'intérêt porté aux produits du terroir au Maroc est dû à leur participation au développement économique et social du pays. Les Signes Distinctifs d'Origine et de Qualité (SDOQ) font partie des stratégies de valorisation de ces produits. Ils protègent à la fois les produits des coopératives et leurs consommateurs.

Cet article vise à étudier à la fois les croyances des Marocains envers les produits labellisés d'origine locale et les facteurs qui pourraient empêcher leur consommation. Pour cela, notre recherche se base sur la théorie du comportement planifié d'Ajzen (1991).

Compte tenu du nombre limité d'études sur la consommation desdits produits au Maroc, notre objectif est de nous rapprocher du consommateur marocain. Nous avons donc opté pour 17 groupes de discussion composés de trois personnes chacun.

Les participants ont exprimé une attitude favorable envers ces produits. Cependant, il existe des barrières qui peuvent empêcher l'acte d'achat. Ainsi, le manque de confiance envers les organismes publics est le facteur le plus cité par les répondants. Il est suivi par la proximité et le prix exorbitant des produits labellisés. D'un point de vue managérial, la connaissance de ces croyances formées sur les produits locaux labellisés permettra à tous les acteurs d'adapter leurs offres en fonction des attentes des consommateurs. Ce qui, espérons-le, incitera les Marocains à consommer des produits locaux et à participer au développement économique et social.

Mots clés : comportement du consommateur ; labellisation ; l'intention ; produits locaux : croyances.

Introduction

The practice of consuming Locally Grown Products (LGP) is a concept that researchers have been focusing on in the past few decades. Locally Grown Products are valued over imported product largely due to the fact that the origin and methods of growing of said products can easily be verified and monitored, which gives such products more value. To ensure and certify the origin of LGP, a system of labeling has been implemented to guarantee and certify their quality and origin.

Morocco, where agriculture is a staple of the economy, has also implemented and benefited from labeling its LGP. Under the Green Moroccan Plan (PMV), more than 60 local products have, so far, been labeled since its launch in 2008. The Protected Geographical Indication (PGI) and the Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) are the main distinctive signs of quality and origin, awarded to local Moroccan products.

The practice of food consumption is a complex behavior (Amilien, 2003 ; Ferrandi, 2013 ; Gravel, 2013 ; Lahlou, 1994 ; Poulain, 2002). In order to study this behavior, researchers have emphasized the importance of multiple facets of food consumption (Fischler, 1996). Consuming food goes beyond fulfilling physiological needs, it also plays a major role psychologically. As my mother always said, a good meal fills your stomach and nurtures your soul.

Ferrandi (2013) states that the act of consuming food is a social and psychological act that has, at the same time, a nutritional, hedonistic and symbolic function. Consuming LGP is a practice that fulfills most, if not all, these functions (Aurier et al., 2004 ; Bérard & Marchenay, 2007 ; Errays & Hattabou, 2015 ; ERTUS et al., 2017 ; Turgeon, 2010).

In this paper, we will present the findings of several focus groups research on the subject of the influence of food labeling on consumers. We will explore the motivations, incentives as well as disincentives and deterrents that influence the consumer's decision.

Our study is based on Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (1991) in order to answer our research question: "when it comes to LGP labels, what are the factors that influence the consumer's decision making process?". Thus, by using a qualitative approach based on focus groups.

This paper is structured as follows: the first section concerns the theoretical aspects and the second one presents the method used to answer to our problematic research. Finally the results are briefly discussed at the conclusion.

1. Theoretical framework

1.1. The Theory of Planned Behavior

Intention is the stage that precede any behavioral act. Whether you wish to take a shower or get dressed. The concept of “Intention” appears in several theories relating to consumer behavior.

For manufacturers of goods, studying a potential purchaser’s intention is a crucial step in anticipating the actions of potential consumers. An individual’s behavioral intention refers to the level at which he or she is willing to perform a behavior and the level of effort he or she is willing to expend to do so (Ajzen, 1991).

In order to better understand the factors that influence the decision to purchase and consume a certain local product, we implement the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) which will help us to analyze and break down this complicated process.

According to the principals of the Theory of Planned Behavior, human behavior is driven by three belief patterns, as presented in the Figure 1. These patterns influence each component of the theory. First, there are behavioral beliefs that constitute the attitude toward behavior. Second, there are normative beliefs that express the way in which the individual deals with social pressure social norms. And finally, control beliefs correspond to the factors that will facilitate the adoption of the behavior or prevent it. The behavioral flow chart below simplifies this theory.

Figure 1 : the theory of planned behavior diagram

Source: by Icek Ajzen (2019)

It should be noted that these beliefs are specific to each type of behavior, thus they should not be generalized (Pavlou & Fygenon, 2006). The behavior we are focused on is food consumption. A behavior that is influenced by a myriad of physiological, psychological and sociological factors.

Therefore, as a preliminary phase, we conducted an elicitation study through interviews and focus groups that identified key beliefs associated with the purchase and consumption of LGP, as suggested by Fishbein and Ajzen (2010).

1.2. The Components of the Theory of Planned Behavior

1.2.1. Behavioral Attitude

The first component of the Theory of Planned Behavior is the attitude towards a behavior. This refers to the balance between positive and negative values of the performance of this behavior. This balance is influenced by the individual's beliefs regarding a certain product or action. These beliefs are the result of information stored, consciously and/or unconsciously, in the individual's memory. One's own experiences, and those of others, play an important role in the formation of this belief.

Attitudes strongly influence what a certain individual will perceive, listen to, and act upon in a way that will make sense in their world (Allport, 1935). Behavioral beliefs are also related to the other components of the Theory of Planned Behavior, as represented in the behavioral flow chart above. For example, if the price of a product is the primary factor for a certain consumer, he or she will base their purchase decision on the monetary value they place on a that product. Therefore, the consumer will classify this type of products as either expensive and not accessible or affordable and accessible.

1.2.2. Social Norms

The second component of the Theory of Planned Behavior is Subjective Norms. This relates to a set of social components of behavioral intentions that can be interpreted as perceived social norms (usually by significant individuals or groups, such as parents, friends, classmates or the public). These norms support or oppose a particular behavior.

Morocco is a cultural country, characterized by several traditions and rites that greatly vary throughout its twelve regions. At its core, the Moroccan society is highly influenced by its Islamic religious beliefs which seeps into its legislative building block. Many, if not most, of the behavioral acts and laws of any Muslim society is based on the teachings and guidelines

of the Holy Quran and Hadith¹. The value of many products has been decreed by texts and passages from the Holy Quran and Hadith. Certain products such as dates, honey and figs are valuable while others such as pork products and wine are forbidden and have virtually no value.

Each individual belongs to a certain social group that consciously, and/or unconsciously, influence their beliefs; which in turn influences their intentions and decision making. The intentions are often guided by the beliefs and values shared among the same social group. Collectivist culture has an influence on consumer buying behavior (Vaissière, 2011).

In their study on consumption factors of sustainable products, Zhang & Zhou (2019) cited some factors that influence the gap between consumption intention and behavior. Some of these factors can be the product price, product information, availability (proximity), difficulty to change habits, inability to plan, perceived product quality and lack of trust in green products.

Gracia & De Magistris (2007) created a Model of Consumer Behavior for organic food products based on the TPB (Figure 2). This Model contains many variables that can influence the consumer's intention to purchase organic foods. These variables depend on the consumer's lifestyle, the type of accessible information, the socio-demographic characteristics, etc.

¹ The textes according to the prophet Mohammed.

Figure 2 : . Empirical model of consumer behavior for organic food products.

Source: (Gracia & De Magistris, 2007)

In this study, we are focused on the factors that influence the intentions of an individual, as cited in the Theory of Planned Behavior. The attributes of the individual's knowledge as well as the resources available to said individual were presented in a previously submitted paper (Raif & Ait Heda, 2021).

2. Methodology and Results

2.1. The Qualitative Approach

To answer our research questions we have chosen to adopt a qualitative approach. This choice is based on many reasons as follows: it allows an ease in the expression; the researcher can interact with the interviewer and can manage the interview by re-launch the debate or ask for more details; the consumer behavior needs to be expressed by acting and by emotions which can be difficult in a quantitative approach.

We chose to focus on the Theory of Planned Behavior to better study the factors that determine the consumption intentions of local products of Moroccan corporations. Since our study falls within the framework of consumer behavior, we used a qualitative study mainly utilizing focus groups.

The qualitative approach allows the researcher to be in direct contact with the subject of research, in this case the consumer. In scientific research, we utilize questionnaires and

interviews to collect data. This allows for a direct and organic interaction between the researcher and the subjects. Naturally, this process was conducted with the subjects' consent (Romelaer, 2019).

With this qualitative approach, samples of subjects freely express themselves. This allows the researcher to better understand the subjects' consumption factors and thus understand what motivates or deters a subject's intent, choice and decision.

The data gathered can help us draw concrete conclusions about the purchase intention of consumers when it relates to labeled local products in Morocco. This way, we can discuss the results of our empirical study in relation to the components of the Theory of Planned Behavior.

For this study, we compiled 17 focus groups composed of three subjects per group. The experiment was concluded once the data became saturated. We spread our analysis of these sample groups between three major cities; Rabat, Casablanca and Fes/Meknes. We focused on these cities because they represent the center of the Moroccan culture and the main urban settlements. The lifestyle of the citizens in this cultural hub is influenced by a modern way of food consumption highly dictated by stress or resulting from the fast and demanding urban lifestyle as well as a desire to maintain a healthy diet. Also, these areas are quite familiar with labels used by corporations selling products from around the country.

We conducted a thematic analysis, according to the three main components of the Theory of Planned Behavior. The coding was done by using NVIVO.10 software, which facilitated the organization of and the illustration of the collected data, either through graphs or tables.

2.2. Interpretation of the results

We will present the main findings of our study according to the themes of our analysis.

2.2.1. Subjective norms

Members of a certain society share a symbiotic relationship with that society. Each member influences, and is influenced, by the collective. This influential exchange is both conscious, by own conviction, or unconscious, by habit.

❖ Social Participation:

There are other social reasons that influence the intent and decision making of consumers. One of the most cited factors by participants was the desire to help small-scale, independent producers, especially women who tend to produce and market their goods.

"I prefer to go directly to the producer, particularly the women in need, I prefer to pay them directly"

Another participant in the same group expressed a reluctance amongst Moroccans to help each other. He cited that it is:

“Impossible according to my beliefs, if you ask a Moroccan to help you he will refuse. That’s how we are, it’s citizenship”

For some participants, it is important to help and encourage corporations. As expressed Khalid from the city of Sale. According to him, it’s:

“the product of corporations should be encouraged”

Almost all participants mentioned the importance of the sense of civic duty towards people in need, both the employees of corporations and independent producers. Mr. Mohamed (Full name, and who is he?) emphasized on this point by citing that:

The camaraderie is important. If a woman is selling chicken for 70 MAD I wouldn’t mind giving her 80 MAD...I know that she will use this money for her children, either to buy clothes or books”.

This sentiment was echoed by Sadik from Rabat

“We should also purchase products from cooperatives, they employ and support families”.

or by Achraf:

“We should help each other. For example, I prefer to buy eggs from a small street cart vendor over a supermarket. Help the little guy”.

Ismail from Casablanca also expressed the pleasure he gets from helping small farmers

“... the thing for me is to buy directly from farmers. It cuts the middle man and puts more money in the farmer’s pockets”.

Mokhtar from Temara also said:

“I too like to buy directly from farmers, buy from them to help them”.

❖ **The Influence of Cultural Practices:**

It is almost impossible for the individual to escape from the influence of the cultural practices of the community to which he belongs. In particular, practices that refer to religion, traditions, rituals, etc. Food consumption is influenced by the cultural affiliation of the consumer (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980; Davis & Jai, 2014; Fischler, 1996; Poulain, 2002).

According to our results, religion and traditions are also factors that influence the consumption of certain local products such as olive oil, dates, honey, almonds, etc. The olive

oil for example, is cited in the Quran and by the prophet Mohamed. He said: “**Take oil of olive and massage with it – it is a blessed tree**” (Darimi, 69:103)

❖ **Pleasure and habits:**

The pleasure of consuming locally grown products especially when we have the personal interaction with the sellers is rooted in our culture, as mentioned by Mohamed from Rabat:

“We put our boots on and go to the market, it makes us feel good. The product is in front of you...in a traditional way”

In general, the consumption of local products provides a certain pleasure and pride. We grow up going to the local markets with our mothers. It was a bonding experience that is rooted in our memory. We learned the difference between ripe and juicy, green and fragrant. We take pride in knowing the different types of tomatoes and we even know which region grows which variant. We even brag to each other that we can shop better than they can. It's a rite of passage for most Moroccans. This same sentiment was common amongst many of the participants in our study. Generally speaking, the pleasure factor stems from our culture, the sense of community, the feeling of helping each other, the pride in our locally grown products, the euphoria of personal interaction and overall, the feeling that we are all part of the same community.

2.2.2. The Norms of Perceived Control:

Now let's discuss factors that deter the consumer and discourages him or her from making the decision to purchase a certain product. Among these factors are lack of trust, prices and proximity.

❖ **Affordability:**

Almost all participants agreed on that products from big corporations tend to carry a higher price tag. Some participants exclaimed that some basic product have “become a luxury” and that corporations charge too much because they “monopolize the market”.

Some believe that corporation charge more solely because they market their products better. Ads on TV, a fancy packaging or even the simple act of renaming or rebranding a product. There is also the market control that corporations exercise. Large corporation often throw their weight around and control large portions of certain product. This practice is precisely what happened to the trade of Argan oil and Saffron.

“Before Saffron was cheap and affordable. One could buy it directly from farmers for about 10 MAD per gram. Now, because of the corporations, the price exceeds 70 MAD per gram. And they say that's because of the taxes” (Mohamed, employee from Rabat)

However, there are those who are willing to pay more despite the fact that they prefer local products. For some people, it's better to get a ready product with controlled quality without the hassle of bargaining or the fear of picking an inferior product.

❖ Physical Accessibility

Although most of the participants in our study showed a favorable attitude towards the consumption of local products, some expressed how inconvenient and difficult it can be to obtain certain items because that are not well marketed and made readily available by a large corporation. According to Faouzi (2021), the proximity of corporations is appreciated by consumers. It guarantees the authenticity of the product and the direct gain by the producers. The abovementioned participant prefers to buy directly from the small producer in order to help him. If the latter is not nearby, the individual will not be encouraged and motivated by this social participation. Let's take Argan oil for example. Since Argan trees only grow in the south of Morocco, it would be extremely inconvenient for someone to travel from a northern city just to purchase some oil. Having a large corporation mass producing Argan oil makes it readily available for most consumers in all regions of the country. For a higher price, of course.

As explained, the perceived norms of control not only affect intention and behavior, but also the two other components of the Theory of Planned Behavior. As for proximity, participants all agreed that there aren't enough corporations in their cities, especially, in Fes, Meknes and Sale.

The lack of the physical accessibility is seen as a deterrent by our participants. Of course, this inconvenience has its exception. The city of Casablanca, being the economic engine of Morocco, has plenty of large markets where one can, pretty much, find anything they desire from any region of the country. The following table 1 presents some examples of participants' statements on the effect of the proximity on the intention to purchase and consume different products produced by large corporations.

Table 1 : exemples of interviewer's verbatim

Participant	Verbatim	Synthesis
Employee (Casablanca)	<i>"...People travel to get fresh produce. I feel that to get fresh products from the source, one needs to travel to remote places where producers still live a simple life and use traditional growing methods"</i>	Local products are found in rural area. People feel that they need to travel to get their hands on locally grown quality products.
Engineer (Fez)	<i>"Once, I bought Amlou from a corporation in Agadir during an exhibition I attended. It was made on the spot in front of me. Next time I buy it, will be made fresh? How will I know? Should I just wait and attend the next exhibition?"</i>	Many corporations promote their product by participating in local exhibitions but these products may not be readily available on a larger scale in a way that is available to customers.
Executive (Casablanca)	<i>"for example, I'm not willing to travel far to a corporation's headquarters just to buy their product"</i>	The Corporation's location can be a deterrent for customers interested in purchasing a certain product.
Worker (Rabat)	<i>"...a certain corporation was offering their products in a hyper market. I bought dates, date syrup and date sugar. The quality was amazing. Unfortunately, when I went back to get more, that corporation no longer offered its products on that specific hyper market"</i>	The customer expressed satisfaction after purchasing a certain product from a specific location but, unfortunately, future purchases were problematic due to the lack of regular and reliable availability.
Employer (Rabat)	<i>"I usually buy the olive oil from Tiflet, a city that is close by"</i>	When this customer decides to purchase olive oil, the proximity is the main factor of choice.

Source: authors

❖ **Trust:**

We were able to deduce that the majority of the participants in our study preferred consuming local products. The tendency to follow an organic diet and healthier lifestyle was a sentiment shared amongst most.

“I prefer local products, so you have to buy them from people you trust” (Executive, Casablanca).

They also believe that consuming local organic products helped prevent diseases and maintained better health overall.

However, it is worth noting that there is a general lack of information regarding the use of labels on local products (Raif et al., 2021). Our participants were not familiar with the Moroccan labels and what each label means. This created a lack of confidence in them, if you don't understand what a label means, it's basic useless to you.

In addition, the fact that these labels are managed by public institutions is another reason why consumers are turned off by this concept. People, generally, tend to mistrust the government.

There are some who do not trust labels in a categorical way. Many has experienced shady and unethical practices that left them with less than satisfactory experience:

“when I went to a corporation to buy Amlou, they gave me a sample to taste and it was delicious, but the one I bought tasted different... I want to help the economy of my country, but they don't deserve it. You can't trust these people when you are watching them cheating and swindling you” (House wife, Casablanca).

We repeatedly noticed that this interviewee's experience was shared by others. Many people want to buy from corporation and help stimulate the economy but the lack of trust is a major issue:

“I like to buy from corporations to encourage them, but most of them don't deserve it” (employee, Temara).

Other consumers feel more comfortable purchasing local products that have foreign (European) labels. Many consumers trust European organizations more than the local government. The belief is that European organization are more trust worthy because they have high standards.

“...I trust foreign labels because they adhere to the standards of hygiene. I fully trust their product and I know they are healthy. When they say something is organic I know I can trust it will be” (Housewife, Casablanca)

Our interviewees don't have much trust in the local public agencies. The majority of Moroccan consumers believe that there is too much corruption and fraud amongst these public agencies.

"...If a product the same price, I will choose a foreign labeled product... they respect the standards set by the local authorities and everything is meticulously monitored for quality" (official, Temara).

For others, especially young people, they prefer to ask their relatives for recommendations and trust friends and acquaintances:

"...I know so and so's brother. He owns a farm, so I can trust him" (employee, Sale).

"if you know the seller, it is not worth having the packaging and labels"(craftsman, Fez).

Alimentation behavior is considered as a social behavior, it is not simply associated with the satisfaction of a physiological need, but it is also a complex act that refers to psychological, social and cultural realities (Vaissière, 2011). According to the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991), the prediction of the realization of this type of behavior is preceded by the three variables cited before. Studying these allows to predict whether or not the individual can form a favorable intention toward the consumption of a food product.

However the lack of information and the trust toward the government may prevent the intention formation. Some interviewees stated that they do not know the labeled products neither the cooperatives. According to Trinquier (2000) in (Zendah Sfar & Zghal, 2012) misinformation in the food field is expressed by the fact that the consumer does not always understand the very technical explanations of professors or other specialists which only aggravates this decline in confidence in the food environment. There is a great need to inform the consumer in a simple way and adapted to all intellectual levels.

In addition, there is a great interest, even a necessity for promotion programs to increase the channels of promotion.

Conclusion

Purchase Intention is the stage that precedes any behavioral act, and is a concept that appears in several theories used to explain consumer behavior.

For producers, studying Purchase Intentions is a crucial step in anticipating the actions of potential consumers. An individual's behavioral intention refers to the level at which he or she is willing to perform a behavior and the level of effort he or she is willing to expend to do so (Ajzen, 1991). According to Halawany-Darson (2010) the multitude and diversity of

experiences lived, differently, by individuals alone or in social connections lead to different perceptions and meanings to object.

In order to study the Moroccan consumer's intention to purchase labeled local products, we conducted focus group interviews with Moroccan consumers. For Faouzi, (2021, p. 281), “*local products in Morocco, whether they are food, therapeutic or everyday products, enjoy a specific iconic positioning that is reflected in their authentic and original cachets in the different perceptions of consumers*”.

The analysis of the interviews showed that many factors culminate to the Moroccan consumers' lack of confidence in product labeling. Amongst these factors we find lack of trust in government, lack of information about labels and their meaning, strong influences from religion and regional habits to name but a few.

Trust, accessibility to labeled local products and their prices are the main deciding factors perceived by our participants. The lack of trust in labels and cooperatives, as well as availability of products are the main obstacles facing productivity despite the fact that the role of the labels is to protect and guarantee quality and origin (Chameroy & Chandon, 2010; Larceneux, 2004).

Following the findings of our study, it appears that the state agencies responsible for the development and promotion of local products must rework their strategies. This will, hopefully, encourage Moroccans to consume local products and participate in the social and economic development. The same is true for corporations, they must make more effort to gain the trust of Moroccan consumers by guarantying and maintaining product quality standards as well availability.

This research has a managerial effect. Specially for the cooperatives in Morocco, they can understand the needs of consumers and then adapt their strategies. The study of factors (motivations/promoters) that influence consumer behavior is essential in marketing. This allows the adaptation of marketing strategies and actions. It is therefore interesting for several stakeholders to identify these factors in order to fine-tune their offers. In otherwise, it may offer appropriate information in order to develop a better public policies related to local foods. For Mounaim et al. (2021) understanding the different ways of communication with consumers are examples of important factors that must be considered by companies, in the relationship with the consumer.

In this conclusion, we would like to reiterate that the description of the formation of consumption intentions and attitudes towards labelled local products has not been presented a

complete way. Indeed, in-depth studies could be conducted in order to understand the relationship between the Moroccan consumer and the cooperatives of local products. Thus, as a research perspective, we recommend a netography to measure the influence of different virtual communities in the formation of certain food consumption behaviors. Especially, according to the remarkable influence of social networks on the said behaviors

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